

RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN ORGANIC KNOWLEDGE AND PURCHASE INTENTION: A STUDY REGARDING ORGANIC FOODS IN CHENNAI

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Abstract

Knowledge plays an important role in influencing the purchase of any type of product. The knowledge regarding the pros and cons of any product makes them to think over and then purchase the product as per their needs. The same principle applies in the context of the purchase of organic food products. The consumers initially gather information about the benefits of the organic products and then they intend to make the purchase of organic food products. The study has been done among the organic food product's consumers in Chennai. The respondents are selected through simple random sampling and the sample size is fixed at 100. The respondents are selected through simple random sampling and the data is collected through a questionnaire. The information so collected is put into regression method of analysis. The findings of the study reveal the fact that there is a significant relationship between organic knowledge and purchase intention.

Keywords: Organic Knowledge, Purchase Intention

INTRODUCTION

The basic requirements for a human to survive in the world are water, air and food. The first two requirements, that is, water and air are available naturally, but, the process of searching food is considered as to be difficult, in the sense, what to consume and what not to. Food is the basic need of all living organisms and is the basic necessity for human life. As far as the human life is considered, food plays a major role. The term food has been defined as any type of nutritious thing which the individuals or the animals drink or eat or something which the plants absorb for maintaining their life as well as growth (Oxford Dictionary, 2016).

The life of humans has transformed to a great extent. The agriculturalists have started to utilize novel technologies, synthetic fertilizers as well as chemicals for increasing their production. The regular consumption of the food products filled with chemicals leads to degradation issues for human beings as well as for the environment (Ali, 2010). For overcoming this problem, the concept of organic farming was implemented which reduces or totally avoids the usage of chemicals and synthetic fertilizers for the production of food products. Hence, in recent times, the consumers have started to become increasingly aware of the food safety and health-related issues (Gil et al., 2002). They have also started to make increased demand for the organic food products for the betterment of human health as well as environment wellness.

In recent times, the pattern of food consumption has changed a lot due to the health-related issues, concern about the individuals regarding the food's nutritional value and the environmental influence. The issues like the quality and the safety of food products attract the interest of the consumers regarding the organic food products. The organic food products are considered to be free from the chemical residues and the pesticides (Fotopoulos and Krystallis, 2002; Zotos et al., 1999). The term organic is considered as a labeling concept which describes the products which are manufactured under the authority of the Organic Foods Production Act. The key guidelines for the production of organic products are to utilize substances and follow practices which will improve the ecological balance and the next guideline is to integrate the farming elements into the ecological whole (Goldman and Clancy, 1991).

Organic Knowledge

The products which are organic in nature are generally safe and healthier too. But, it is also a fact that the knowledge about the use of organic food products is very limited among the consumers. The absence of the functional knowledge about the organic products among the consumers is regarded to be the major drawback which restricts them from the purchase of such products. Further, most of the consumers do not even know the exact meaning and usage of the organic food products (Klockner and Ohms, 2009; Janssen and Hamm, 2012). This absence of information can be explained in the context of two facets. The first one being the consumers are not aware of the information regarding the system of organic farming and the methods of cultivating such products. The second one being the reflection of the baffled mental state of the consumers in the context of safe food 'labels. Such labels seem to ensure in providing similar health benefits as that of organic food labels.

The consumers have the belief that the yield is low in organic farming when compared with the conventional food growing system. The opinion of the consumers about the organic food production consumes more amount of hard work as well as time when compared with the chemical farming system (Baker et al., 2004; Jahn and Kunz, 2012; Mondelaers et al., 2009). Prior to the commencement of the organic method of farming, the farmers have to invigorate their farming fields and also have to make the soil free from chemicals and pesticides. The whole process of organic farming needs two to three years for a farming field which was earlier used for farming with chemicals and pesticides.

Purchase intention

The term purchase intention refers to the decision taken by the consumers for purchasing a brand or a product. The measurement of purchase intention is somewhat a difficult process since the measurement technique depends on several factors. Several external and internal factors prove to be accountable and affecting the purchase decision of the consumers. Thøgersen in the year 2009 had stated that the attitude and behavior perception of the consumers establish the purchase intention of the consumers. The purchase intention of the consumers is affected by the consumer's attitude and the product's price. Ajzen in 1991 had proposed the TPB (theory of planned behavior). This theory predicted the purchase intention of the consumers based on the behavioral factors. The control and normative beliefs are assessed with

the help of the determinants of PBC (perceived behavioral control), subjective norms and attitude. TPB indicated that the three factors mentioned here have got the ability to appraise the behavioral intentions of the consumers.

STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

Definitely, the market for organic foods is growing in a rapid pace in developing nations like India and has also got reasonable number of consumers for such products with higher level of production capability in the farmland. Hence, it becomes significant to explore the factors that influence the purchase intention of the consumers regarding organic foods. After the literature review has been done, the current research has been done to investigate the knowledge of the consumers and their purchase intention regarding the organic products.

NEED FOR THE STUDY

In the past twenty years, the organic industry has been observed to gain rapid growth throughout the world. Amongst the Indian organic segment, the organic foods are emerging at a fast pace. It is also seen to attract increased number of consumers and the marketers, as far as India is concerned. The industry for organic food comprises of varied diversity of the food products like basmati rice, pulses, honey, spices, tea, coffee, vegetables, fruits, oilseeds, processed food, herbal medicines and cereals.

OBJECTIVES

The aim of the study was to identify the relation of organic knowledge with the purchase intention of the consumers regarding the purchase of organic food products.

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

Wijaya et al., (2017) had done a study for examining a model that exhibits the impacts of organic knowledge, attitude, subjective norm and PBC on the purchase intention of the consumers towards the organic food products. The authors had performed an explorative study and had collected the data through a questionnaire. The sample population of the study was the housewives who consumed organic products. The study was conducted in Jakarta, Surabaya and Yogyakarta in Indonesia. The data was analyzed with the help of SEM. The findings of the study showed that the purchase intention of the consumers towards the organic food products was indirectly predicted by the organic knowledge of the consumers. PBC, attitude, subjective norms and organic knowledge positively contributed towards the organic food's purchase intention.

Shan Lijie et al., (2020) explored the relationship of the attitude of the consumers towards the organic food with their purchase intention with respect to the effect of anchoring and framing effect as well as the role played by knowledge. The findings of the study suggested that both the benefits in purchasing the organic food and loss due to non-purchase of organic food affected the purchase intention and the attitude of the consumers towards the organic food

products. Further, the judgment of the consumers was also affected by the presentation of the anchor price in the advertisements. The findings of this study indicated that a message which is framed in a negative manner had got the tendency to induce a favorable purchase intention and attitude when compared with a message which has been positively framed. It was also explored that an anchor price which was low was highly favorable than an anchor price which was high. To conclude, the authors had identified that the consumers who had low level of knowledge regarding organic food products were highly susceptible to the anchoring and framing effects. The findings of the study provided suggestions for establishing proper messages as well as price anchoring for enhancing the organic food consumption.

Sajeeb Kumar Shrestha (2020) had made a study for measuring the purchase intention of the consumers towards the organic food products. The author had used a research design which was causal and descriptive in nature. The data of the study was primary in nature and was collected through a cross-sectional and structural in nature. The sample size of the study was 200. The respondents were selected through convenience sampling. The econometric and psychometric dimensions of the suggested model of the research study were tested using the PLS-SEM instrument. The findings of the study revealed that the availability of the product, trust on it and environmental concern were the significant predictors for the purpose of motivating the purchase intention regarding organic foods. It was also explored that awareness and health concern did not support the purchase intention towards organic food products.

Naveed Ahmed et al., (2020) had proposed the extended model of TPB. This study facilitated to examine the Chinese students regarding their purchase intention towards the organic food products. The respondents were between the age of 18 and 30. The sample size of the study was 515 and the analysis was done through SEM. The results of the study showed that PBC (perceived behavioral control), attitude and subjective norms had optimistic impacts over the purchase intention of the Chinese students towards the organic food products. Further, it was also explored that attitude had an optimistic impact over the environmental concern. Also, environmental concern was also explored to affect the purchase intention of the Chinese students towards the organic food products. Results revealed that environmental concern mediated the relationship of purchase intention and attitude of the consumers towards organic products in an optimistic manner. To be more significant, the association of attitude, subjective norms and perceived behavioral control with the purchase intention was found to be moderated by the environmental awareness.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The purpose of the study is to explore the effect of organic knowledge on the purchase intention of the consumers towards organic products. The present study has been done with the help of a questionnaire. The respondents of the study are the consumers of organic products in Chennai. The data collected through questionnaire is analyzed with the help of Multiple Regression. Knowledge Scale was adopted from

ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATION

R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	F	Sig.
.965(a)	.931	.926	178.087	.000(a)

a Predictors: (Constant), Organic knowledge

	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
(Constant)	-.183	.135		-1.354	.179
I know pretty much about organic food	.153	.034	.212	4.500	.000
I know how to judge the quality of organic food	.159	.056	.160	2.860	.005
I think I know enough about organic food to feel pretty confident when I make a purchase	.200	.032	.298	6.263	.000
I do feel very knowledgeable about organic food	.170	.047	.176	3.641	.000
Among my circle of friends, I'm one of the "experts" on organic food	.094	.043	.091	2.174	.032
I have heard of most of the new organic foods that are around	.093	.029	.105	3.261	.002
I can tell whether organic food is worth the price	.175	.041	.175	4.239	.000

Dependent Variable: Purchase Intention

Findings show that all statement of organic knowledge on purchase intention was significant. The table also shows a positive coefficient, which means that all statements of knowledge were influence on the purchase intention in Chennai. There was a relation found between the dependent variable and the organic knowledge. The analysis done through regression exhibits that among seven factors, all factors was highly influence over the Purchase intention. The coefficient value, R square, was found to be 0.931 through multiple regressions, which shows that 93.1% of the independent variables had an influence on the purchase intention of Chennai. In order to examine whether the value of coefficient (R^2) is significant or not, ANOVA was executed. The F value so got was 178.087 which means $p < 0.000$. This finding shows that there was a significant relation between the dependent and the independent variable. It was also reported that organic knowledge was seen to predict purchase intention. The findings of the research are thus: there is a significant relationship between organic knowledge and purchase intention.

CONCLUSION

The organic knowledge has been found to influence the purchase of the organic products. When the consumers become aware of the benefits and advantages of using organic products, for them and for the environment as a whole, they tend to purchase them more, as their intention to purchase such products gets increased. Hence, the producers and marketers of the organic products are suggested to provide extensive information about the organic products which they

produce and offer in the market. The result of the research is that there is a significant relationship between organic knowledge and purchase intention.

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